

Synergistic Effects in Oxygen Evolution Activity of Mixed Iridium-Ruthenium Pyrochlores

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ABSTRACT Pyrochlore oxides ($A_2B_2O_7$) simultaneously containing iridium and ruthenium in the B-site are promising catalysts for oxygen evolution reaction (OER) in acid media. The catalytic activity of the pyrochlore based catalysts is increased by the coexistence of Ir and Ru in the B-site of the pyrochlore structure. Lanthanide (Yb, Gd, or Nd) stabilized mixed pyrochlores with a fraction of Ru in the B-site of $x_{Ru}=0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8$ were synthesized by the spray-freeze freeze-dry approach. All prepared mixed pyrochlore catalysts are surpassing the OER activity of the corresponding iridium and ruthenium analogues featuring no cation mixing as well as that of the benchmark IrO_2 catalyst. The synergy of Ir and Ru in the B-site of the pyrochlore structure suppresses the effect of the A-site cation radius on the OER activity. The observed OER activity scales with the Ir-Ru bond distance which represents the local structure of the prepared materials. The most active ytterbium catalyst also shows a significant stability improvement under OER operando conditions over the benchmark IrO_2

1. Introduction

Efficient electricity storage in chemical bonds is of vital importance for the replacement of fossil fuels with renewable energy sources.[1,2] Hydrogen is a particularly suitable energy-rich molecule capable of renewable energy storage; the feasibility of its production is a prerequisite for the large scale implementation of energy storage in hydrogen.[3,4] Electrolytic hydrogen production is, however, limited by the sluggish kinetics of the electrocatalytic oxygen evolution reaction (OER)[5,6] which, in contrast to the hydrogen evolution reaction (HER), is difficult to optimize. The oxygen evolution reaction involves four single electron/proton charge-transfer steps and thus requires optimization of the adsorption energies of three different reaction intermediates.[7–9] Rational design of active and sufficiently stable electrocatalysts for OER, therefore, represents one of the major challenges in electrocatalytic research.[10]

The operating conditions of the water electrolyzer, particularly its operating pH (acid or alkaline), significantly influence the scope of available catalyst materials. In alkaline media, one may rely on catalysts based on relatively abundant and inexpensive transition metal oxides,[11] e.g. of Ni,[12,13] Co,[14,15], or Fe[16,17]. The technological implementation of alkaline electrolyzers is, however, hindered by large ohmic losses that restrict the achievable maximum current densities. Electrolyzers operating in acidic media are spared of these restrictions.[2,18] Their reliance on rather expensive and unstable OER catalysts like Pt group oxide catalysts is, however, also impeding their large scale implementation.[11,19]

RuO_2 has been known as the catalyst of the highest activity for oxygen evolution catalysis in acidic media.[20,21] Nevertheless, the less active but considerably more stable IrO_2 is used as the industrial benchmark catalyst for applications today.[22] The feasibility of acid-based electrolyzer operation may be improved if the transition metal loading in the catalyst is reduced or if the lifetime of the catalyst is extended. In this context, one can aim at the improvement of the catalyst's utilization by nano-structuring of the catalyst[21,23,24] or the catalyst's support[25–27] or by increasing the electrode surface area. Alternatively, one can aim at reducing the content of iridium by switching from binary to ternary phases. By introducing elements with a higher abundance in the earth's crust[28–31], ideally, both the catalyst's activity and stability could be improved. While the activity can be improved by the introduction of ruthenium, the stability of such a catalyst would remain an issue.[32] New ternary phases must maintain the high intrinsic activity and stability of IrO_2 to be viable catalytic materials.

Ternary phase catalysts of $\text{A}_2\text{B}_2\text{O}_7$ composition conforming to the pyrochlore family (Fd3m, space group 227) have been proposed as promising catalysts to replace conventional IrO_2 and RuO_2 OER catalysts. [33–39] The cubic pyrochlore structure features two types of cationic sites

and can be described as two interpenetrating networks: a cubic diamondoid A_2O lattice and a lattice of corner connected BO_6 octahedra. This highly flexible structure allows for various combinations of A-site and B-site cations permitting significant variation of the lattice parameter and, consequently, of the material's d-band center. In OER active pyrochlores, Ru (Ir) occupies the B-site of the pyrochlore structure while the structure forming A-site features either divalent (e.g. Pb^{2+}) or trivalent (e.g. Bi^{3+} or rare earth elements) cations.[39] The electrocatalytic properties of pyrochlore-based iridium and ruthenium oxides have been explored for both oxygen reduction[33–35] and oxygen evolution[36–38]. A beneficial effect of A-site[40,41] and B-site[42] doping has been shown for Yttrium pyrochlores. Pyrochlore based OER catalysts employing lanthanides (Yb, Gd, Nd) as A-site cations with either iridium or ruthenium residing in the B-site were recently reported.[43] The prepared pyrochlores showed comparable or higher activity toward OER than the benchmark IrO_2 catalyst, with the observed activity correlating with the unit cell parameter which reflects the position of the catalysts d-band center.[43]

This report describes the synthesis of a new class of rare earth stabilized pyrochlore catalysts conforming to the general composition $Ln_2(Ru_xIr_{1-x})_2O_7$ ($Ln = Yb, Gd, Nd$) i.e., featuring both iridium and ruthenium as B-site cations. The paper shows that the coexistence of Ru and Ir in close proximity not only brings up the OER activity, surpassing the IrO_2 benchmark catalyst but also leads to a significant activity improvement compared with the pyrochlores without Ru/Ir cation mixing. The observed electrocatalytic behavior is related to the local structure of the catalyst. Aside from the superior OER activity of these catalysts with respect to that of the benchmark IrO_2 , their stability may also surpass that of the industrial benchmark. The observed exceptional activity and stability, however, fails to correlate with the diffraction-based structural parameters and is rationalized in terms of synthesis induced local structure changes.

2. Experimental

2.1. Chemicals

Ruthenium nitrosyl nitrate ($\text{Ru}(\text{NO})(\text{NO}_3)_3$, 31.3 at. % Ru, Alfa Aesar), and iridium (III) acetate ($\text{Ir}(\text{OOCCH}_3)_3$, 48.8 at. % Ir, Chempur) were used as the source of ruthenium and iridium, respectively. Ytterbium acetate ($\text{Yb}(\text{OOCCH}_3)_x \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$), gadolinium acetate ($\text{Gd}(\text{OOCCH}_3)_3 \cdot x \text{H}_2\text{O}$), and neodymium acetate ($\text{Nd}(\text{OOCCH}_3)_x \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$) (all Sigma Aldrich, 99.9%) were used as the sources of rare earth elements. The crystal water content, x , of the rare earth metal acetates was determined by thermal analysis using a SetSys Evolution system (Setaram) coupled with a quadrupole mass spectrometer (QMG 700, Pfeiffer) by SuperSonic system (Setaram). Decomposition of the rare earth metal acetates was performed by heating the powders in a temperature range of 30 – 1000 °C (at 10 °C min^{-1}) in an open alumina crucible under inert atmosphere (argon, 60 mL min^{-1}). Evolved gas analysis data were collected in multiple-ion detection mode (MID) as the intensity of individually selected fragments. Values of m/z (mass-to-charge ratios) were pre-selected to: 12, 16, 17, 18, 28 and 44. The actual crystal water content of the lanthanide precursors was found to be $x = 4.0$ for ytterbium acetate, 2.8 for gadolinium acetate, and 1.1 for neodymium acetate.

2.2. Material preparation

The pyrochlore materials were prepared using the spray-freeze freeze-drying approach following the procedure as previously described.[43–45] Precursor solutions, containing both transition metals (Ru and Ir) in the desired ratio and one rare earth metal (Nd, Gd, Yb), were prepared by dissolving the corresponding metal salts in Milli-Q quality deionized water. The total metal concentration was kept at 8 mM for each sample solution. The solutions were stirred

for at least 30 minutes before the spray-freezing step. The sample compositions were adjusted to reach a pre-set fraction of ruthenium in the B-site of the pyrochlore structure. Samples with $x_{Ru} = 0.2, 0.4, 0.6,$ and 0.8 initial concentration of the reaction mixtures were prepared for each lanthanide. The ice precursors were prepared by spraying 100 mL of precursor solution into ca. 2 L of liquid nitrogen. The resulting ice was freeze-dried using a FreeZone Triad Freeze Dry System 7400030 (Labconco) at reduced pressure (1 Pa) following the subsequent temperature protocol: Precooling of the ice precursor to $-30\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ while the cooling chamber was evacuated, followed by gradually increasing the temperature ($-30\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (2 h), $-25\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (5 h), $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (4 h), $-15\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (6 h), $+30\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (4 h)). The obtained precursor-foam was carefully removed from the freeze-dryer and immediately pre-annealed at $300\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ in a muffle furnace for 30 minutes. Afterward, the samples were calcined in a tube furnace in air at $1020\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The exact calcination time was adjusted for each sample to obtain single-phase pyrochlore materials (12 to 24 h).

2.3. Physical characterization

The crystallinity and phase purity of the synthesized materials were analyzed with powder X-ray diffraction (XRD). Diffraction patterns were recorded using a Rigaku Miniflex 600 powder X-ray diffractometer with $\text{Cu K}\alpha$ radiation operating at 30 kV and 10 mA. The unit cell parameters were determined by Rietveld refinement using the Profex 3.0.13 software package.[46] Morphology and particle size of the prepared samples were analyzed using a Hitachi S4800 scanning electron microscope (SEM) equipped with a Nanotrace EDX detector (Thermo Electron). The average sample composition was determined by energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) measured at an accelerating voltage of 25 keV.

2.4. X-ray absorption spectroscopy

Ir L_{III}- and Ru K-edge X-ray absorption spectra (XAS) of all samples were collected at the SuperXAS beamline of the Swiss Light Source (SLS) (PSI, Villigen, Switzerland), which is a third-generation synchrotron operating under top-up mode at 2.4 GeV electron energy and a current of 400 mA. The incident beam was collimated by a Pt-coated mirror for measurements at the Ru K-edge or a Rh coated mirror for measurements at the Ir L_{III}-edge at 2.5 mrad and monochromatized using a channel-cut Si(111) monochromator. The beam was subsequently focused with a Rh-coated (Ir L_{III}-edge) or a Pt-coated (Ru K-edge) toroidal mirror down to 100 x 100 mm at the sample position. Samples were measured at room temperature under ambient pressure in the form of cellulose pellets (100 mg) containing 20-30 mg of respective pyrochlore. All spectra were measured in transmission mode using the Quick scanning XAS (QEXAFS) approach[47] that allowed for the rapid collection of 360 spectra during a measurement time of 3 minutes, which were then averaged. The spectra were measured in an energy range of 11000 – 12300 eV at the Ir L_{III}-edge and 21800 – 23800 eV at the Ru K-edge. At the iridium L_{III}-edge, the beamline energy was calibrated with a Pt reference foil to the Pt L_{III}-edge position at 11564 eV. For measurement at the ruthenium K-edge a Ru foil was used for referencing (22117 eV). The absorption edge energies of the pyrochlore materials were determined from the X-ray absorption near edge structure (XANES) part of the collected spectra, using the maximum of the first derivative of the edge region. Extended X-ray absorption fine structure (EXAFS) data were analyzed using the Demeter program package based on the IFEFFIT libraries,[48,49] which included energy calibration, background subtraction, and edge step normalization. For the fitting, the $\chi(k)$ functions were weighted with k^3 . The k-range used in the for the Fourier transform was adjusted for each refined spectrum independently, according to the quality of the measured

signal. The local structure parameters were refined from EXAFS functions by non-linear least square (NLLS) fitting in the R-space in the range of 1-4 Å. The EXAFS analysis was restricted to phase pure materials. The details of the refinement (k-range, goodness of fit (R-factor), Debye-Waller factors σ , absorption edges E_0 , occupation, and refined values of the effective scattering paths) are listed in the Supporting Information.

2.5. Electrochemical measurements

The activity of the prepared materials in the oxygen evolution reaction was evaluated from linear sweep voltammograms recorded in acid media. A standard single-compartment three-electrode cell was used in all experiments with an Analytics Rotator AFMSRXE RDE-setup of Pine Instruments controlled by an Autolab PGSTAT30.

Thin-film catalysts layers deposited on a glassy carbon RDE support were used as working electrodes. The catalyst ink suspensions were prepared using 10 mg of pyrochlore catalyst, 1.0 mL of Milli-Q quality H₂O, 4.0 mL of isopropyl alcohol ($\geq 99.5\%$, Sigma Aldrich), and 20 μL of 5 wt. % Nafion solution (Nafion 117, Sigma Aldrich). The ink suspensions were sonicated for 30 min before depositing 10.0 μL on a polished glassy carbon disk electrode (0.196 cm²) to reach a total catalyst loading of 100 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$. A platinum mesh was used as the counter electrode and a saturated calomel electrode (SCE) as the reference electrode. All potentials were recalculated and are reported in the reversible hydrogen electrode (RHE) scale. The voltammetric curves were corrected for uncompensated solution resistance. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy measurements were recorded in the range from 15 kHz to 1 Hz with an amplitude of 10 mV to correct for the ohmic drop in solution. Current densities are based on the

geometric surface area of the glassy carbon disk electrode. The 0.1 M HClO₄ electrolyte was prepared from 70 % HClO₄ (puriss. p.a., Sigma Aldrich) by diluting with Milli-Q H₂O.

Cyclic voltammograms were recorded in the potential range of 1.0–1.5 V at 50 mVs⁻¹ until a steady surface capacitance was measured. To estimate the electrochemically active surface area, voltammograms were recorded from 1.0 V to 1.4 V at a 10 mVs⁻¹ scan rate. Corresponding surface capacitances are listed in Table S1. Afterward, voltammograms were recorded at 1 mVs⁻¹ in the potential range of 1.0-1.5 V. The polarization curves were derived from steady-state chronoamperometric measurements, in which the potential was gradually stepped from 1.2 to 1.6 V while holding for 1 min at each potential. Accelerated electrochemical stability tests were conducted by applying a series of 500 subsequent potential-steps of 1.0 and 1.6 V vs. RHE while holding for 10 s at each potential. The values of oxygen evolution current were recorded at 1.6 V after each 20th cycle. In addition, cyclic voltammograms were recorded in the potential range of 1.0–1.4 V at 10 mVs⁻¹ to obtain the data needed to approximate relative changes in the electrochemically active surface area that can occur throughout stability cycling.

2.6. Density Functional Theory calculations

To explain the experimental results at the atomic level, we have performed Density Functional Theory (DFT) calculations using the Quantum Espresso package[50]. The investigated structures were fully relaxed, i.e. unit cell lattices and atomic positions, using the PBEsol[51] exchange-correlation functional and pseudopotentials from the Standard Solid State Pseudopotentials (SSSP accuracy) library[52] adding a Hubbard + U correction of 5 eV applied to the orbitals of the rare earth element. A uniform 6 × 6 × 6 k-point mesh and a Marzari–Vanderbilt smearing of 0.02 Ry were used. We have used a similar methodology to design new rare earth Ir/Ru-based

catalysts for the OER reaction.[43] For each composition, we have calculated all the possible arrangements of the B-ions. In most of the cases, the position of the B-site cations has only limited effects on the electronic properties of these materials. When this was not the case, we have considered only the ground state configuration, keeping in mind that the energy differences between these structures are often below 50 meV. In the calculation of the d-band center, we have considered only the occupied d-states closest to the Fermi level.

3. Results and Discussion

The pyrochlore oxides with Ru/Ir cation mixing were prepared using the spray-freeze freeze-dry approach.[45,44] The finely dispersed amorphous precursors obtained from the freeze-drying step were calcined in air to obtain the crystalline oxide materials. Prolonged calcination at 1020 °C (12-24 h) was necessary to obtain phase pure, pyrochlore structured materials, which was confirmed using powder X-ray diffraction (XRD) (see **Figure 1a-c**). Qualitatively, the experimental diffraction patterns of the mixed pyrochlores conform with that known for the pure pyrochlores. This agrees well with an arrangement where the lanthanide cation occupies the A-site while the transition metal cations reside in the B-sites of the structure. Minor contamination with primary oxides is found for the gadolinium containing samples. Rietveld refinement of the XRD patterns reveals that the maximum contamination is found for the $\text{Gd}_2(\text{Ru}_{0.17}\text{Ir}_{0.73})_2\text{O}_7$ sample with an IrO_2 content of 2 % and a Gd_2O_3 content of 4 %. These minor contaminations are not expected to significantly influence the measured catalytic activities. Details of the Rietveld refinement are included in the Supporting Information (**Figure S1**). The formation of a secondary phase was observed for the Ir-rich neodymium samples (see **Figure 1c**). The secondary phase was assigned to $\text{Nd}_6\text{Ir}_2\text{O}_{13}$, which is known to form alongside the pyrochlore

phase in the Nd-Ir-O phase system.[53] The actual chemical composition of mixed pyrochlores as detected by EDX varied slightly from the composition of the precursor solution. Ruthenium fractions in the B-site occupation of $x_{\text{Ru}} = 0.15, 0.45, 0.58,$ and 0.70 were obtained for ytterbium containing samples. Very similar values were observed regardless of the lanthanide residing in the A-site (see **Figure 1b-c**). The lattice parameters of the synthesized samples as determined from the XRD patterns (**Figure 1d**) were found to depend primarily on the size of the lanthanide cation stabilizing the pyrochlore structure in the A-site. The unit cell parameter a was found to be ca. 10.10 \AA for the Yb pyrochlores, ca. 10.25 \AA for Gd pyrochlores and ca. 10.35 \AA for Nd pyrochlores.

Figure 1 Powder X-ray diffraction patterns of the synthesized pyrochlore phases of $\text{Ln}_2(\text{Ru}_x\text{Ir}_{1-x})_2\text{O}_7$ composition, the actual composition is listed in the figure legends for Ln equal to a) ytterbium b) gadolinium, and c) neodymium. All reflections observed in diffraction patterns of the prepared materials can be indexed within the pyrochlore structural type. Additional reflections arising from secondary phase formation of $\text{Nd}_6\text{Ir}_2\text{O}_{13}$ are marked with an asterisk. d)

Dependence of the unit cell parameter of the synthesized pyrochlore phases with Ir/Ru cation mixing, as determined from XRD patterns, on the sample's ruthenium content, as determined from EDX spectroscopy. e) SEM micrographs depicting the morphologies of the pyrochlore samples with Ru content of $x_{\text{Ru}}=0.70-0.73$ % prepared by the spray-freeze freeze-drying approach with subsequent prolonged annealing at 1020 °C

The observed linearity between the unit cell parameter and the ionic radius of the A-site cation is in agreement with the literature.[39,43] The coexistence of Ru and Ir in the B-site leads to a further variation of the unit cell. The dependence of the unit cell parameter on the composition of the B-site is linear regardless of the type of A-site cation (see **Fig. 1d**). The slope of a vs. x_{Ru} is the same for all three different lanthanides. The observed experimental trends conform to Vegard's law which is characteristic for solid solutions with a homogenous distribution of the cations. The observed lattice expansion can be attributed to the slightly larger ionic radius of Ir (0.63 Å) than that of Ru (0.62 Å),[54] which is consistent with the larger lattice parameter a found for iridium with respect to ruthenium pyrochlores without cation mixing.[43] The pyrochlore samples' morphology and particle size were analyzed using scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Typical SEM pictures for each lanthanide cation of the pyrochlore structured samples are shown in **Figure 1e**. A full presentation of SEM micrographs can be found in the Supporting Information, **Figure S2**. As anticipated from the prolonged annealing at high temperature, the particle sizes of the resulting crystalline material are on the sub-micron scale. The smallest average particle size of ca. 100 nm is found for the samples with ytterbium as the A-site cation, while the gadolinium samples have average particle sizes of 150-250 nm. Particles of about 350 nm size are observed for the samples containing neodymium. This is in good

agreement with the particle sizes detected for the pure ruthenium and iridium pyrochlores.[43] A detailed analysis of the SEM-based particle sizes is given in **Table S1** of the Supporting Information. There seems to be a correlation between the particle size and size of the A-site cation. This tendency apparently suggests a more significant contribution of the surface to the overall energy minimization in the case of pyrochlores stabilized by smaller lanthanides.

Regardless of the A-site cation, the crystals of the prepared materials are of rounded shape without any prevailing faceting. It may be, therefore, expected that ~~surface~~ the surface of the prepared materials integrates contributions from all possible surface orientations.

3.1. X-Ray Absorption Spectroscopy

The local structure of the prepared pyrochlores was determined from the Ir L_{III}-edge and Ru K-edge EXAFS functions. Typical X-ray absorption near edge structure (XANES) spectra are depicted in **Figure 2a-b** for the pyrochlore samples with gadolinium as the A-site cation. An absorption edge energy of 11217 eV is detected at the iridium L_{III}-edge regardless of the catalyst's composition. The edge position is in agreement with previously reported values for iridium pyrochlores and has been ascribed to the Ir +IV oxidation state.[23,37] Similarly, a Ru K-edge energy of 22130 eV was found in all Ru containing pyrochlore samples. This absorption edge energy value has also previously been reported for ruthenium pyrochlore samples and is compliant with the Ru oxidation state of +IV.[37,55] Hence, the average oxidation state of transition metal cation residing in the pyrochlore B-site is independent of the catalyst composition.

The local structure of the B-site environment is reflected in the extended X-Ray absorption fine structure (EXAFS) functions. Typical R-space representations of the EXAFS functions

measured at the Ru (K-edge) and the Ir (L_{III}-edge), respectively, are shown in **Figure 2c-d**. There is no qualitative difference between EXAFS functions extracted from Ru K and Ir L_{III}-edge spectra. This confirms that both Ru and Ir reside in the B-site environment of the pyrochlore structure. Both the Ir and Ru EXAFS functions are dominated by a strong signal located at around 1.7-1.8 Å (without phase correction), corresponding to the scattering from oxygen atoms coordinating the absorbing transition metal. The second scattering event of significant intensity is found at a radial distance of 3.0-3.5 Å and originates from scattering at the neighboring cationic sites. This part of the EXAFS functions is affected by the chemical composition of the prepared pyrochlores. In the case of the iridium EXAFS functions, the metal-metal scattering shifts towards lower metal-metal distances with increasing ruthenium content. A comparable trend can be traced in the ruthenium K-edge data.

Figure 2 Typical XANES spectra of $Gd_2(Ru_xIr_{1-x})_2O_7$ including the pure gadolinium iridate ($x = 0.00$) and gadolinium ruthenate pyrochlore ($x = 1.00$) measured a) at the Ru K-edge and b)

at the Ir L_{III}-edge. Fourier transformed EXAFS functions of the gadolinium pyrochlore samples in R-space, weighed with k^2 , both with and without cation mixing on the B-site measured c) at the Ru K-edge and d) at the Ir L_{III}-edge. No phase-correction was applied. The Ru fraction x is given in the figure legends a)-d). An example of the non-linear least square (NLLS) fit of the experimental Fourier transformed EXAFS function on the Ru K-edge e) and Ir L_{III}-Edge f). EXAFS data are normalized with k^3 (\square) and are shown with their NLLS fit (red line) of the theoretical model using a two-shell model in a fitting range from 1 – 4 Å in R-space. The EXAFS functions correspond to $\text{Yb}_2(\text{Ru}_{0.15}\text{Ir}_{0.85})_2\text{O}_7$ on both e) the Ru K-edge ($R=0.009$) and f) Ir L_{III}-edge ($R=0.015$). All EXAFS functions are presented without phase-correction applied.

The ideal cubic pyrochlore crystal structure assumes equal distances between transition metal cations residing in B-sites; equal distance is also expected for the distance between A-site cations and neighboring B-site cations. These restrictions are embedded in the model employed in the XRD refinement. Hence, the individual bond information (Ru-Ru, Ru-Ir, Ir-Ir, Ln-Ir, Ln-Ru) cannot be refined from diffraction data. The local structure information available from the analysis of the EXAFS part of the X-ray absorption spectra is, however, free of this restriction. The local structure refinement of the EXAFS functions was based on a pyrochlore structural model (see **Figure 2e-f** for typical fits of Ru K-edge and the Ir L_{III}-edge EXAFS functions, respectively). The actual cation distribution in the B-site of mixed pyrochlores was established using independent scattering paths of ruthenium and iridium in the B-site position (see **Tables S2-S3** of the Supporting Information). The refinement results do not suggest any clustering of Ru or Ir in the pyrochlore structure. A statistical distribution of Ir and Ru is found for all samples within the margin of error.

It may be expected that the catalytic behavior of the pyrochlore materials is to be controlled by the electronic structure, which can be related to the arrangement of the catalytically active transition metal cations in the B-site. It needs to be stressed that in an ideal cubic pyrochlore all metal-metal distances (i.e. those between cations in the B-site, but also between the cations residing in the A-sites) are equal. In such a case, the overall structure is controlled by the size of the A-site cation which acts as a spacer directing the position and width of the bands of the pyrochlore's electronic structure. The refined metal-metal scattering distances in mixed pyrochlore samples are compared in **Figure 3**. Due to the nature of the refinement procedure, they allow reflecting on the deviations of the actual local structure in mixed pyrochlores from the ideal pyrochlore.

Figure 3 Bond lengths of Ru-Ru, Ir-Ir, and Ir-Ru residing in the B-site of the pyrochlore structure as obtained from the model of the EXAFS refinement as a function of ruthenium content for **a)** Ytterbium, **b)** Gadolinium, and **c)** Neodymium. The B-site bond distances of the samples without cation mixing are included for pure ruthenium and iridium pyrochlores as $x_{Ru} = 1$ and $x_{Ru} = 0$, respectively.

As follows from **Figure 3**, there are several trends one can extract from the refined metal-metal distances. The average distance of Ir-Ir pairs of atoms in mixed pyrochlores is, in general, longer than that of Ru-Ru pairs. This difference is rather small in the ytterbium stabilized mixed

pyrochlores but increases with increasing size of the A-site cation. This contrasts the prediction of an ideal pyrochlore model which is embedded in the diffraction data analysis. It needs to be noted that the average Ru-Ru pair distances essentially coincide with those obtained for pure pyrochlores, i.e. for materials featuring no coexistence of Ru and Ir in the B-site positions. It also needs to be noted that the Ru-Ru distances are insensitive to the ratio of Ru and Ir in the B-site. The same cannot be said of the neighboring Ir-Ir pair distances which tend to increase with increasing Ru content, namely if larger cations reside in the A-site. In contrast to the Ir-Ir distances, the Ru-Ir pair distances remain relatively short and mostly coincide with the Ru-Ru distances.

The standard deviations of the refined coordinating M-M distances of the mixed pyrochlores exceed those observed for Ru-Ru and Ir-Ir distances in pure pyrochlores. This suggests that the mixed pyrochlores are significantly less ordered than their pure counterparts. Qualitatively different behavior is encountered in the Nd stabilized mixed pyrochlores where the refinement returns the shortest distance for the Ru-Ir pairs while Ru-Ru and Ir-Ir pairs are apparently longer. The difference between individual B-site cationic pairs remains, however, comparable with the standard deviations, which suggests a high variability of the bonding arrangements in the Nd stabilized mixed pyrochlores. Alternatively, one can outline the deviation from the ideal pyrochlore structure by correlating metal-metal distances. (see **Figure S3**). The deviations of the local structure (from that of an ideal pyrochlore) may be interpreted in terms of a local stress/strain which seems to be located primarily along with the Ru-Ir pairs. The Ir-Ir pairs, in turn, tend to compensate for the non-ideality of the structure in the mixed pyrochlores. The non-ideal local structure is more pronounced in a looser pyrochlore structure utilizing relatively large A-site cation.

3.2. Electrocatalytic Behavior

The mixed Ir/Ru pyrochlores are active in oxygen evolution. The catalytic activity was determined from linear scan voltammetry data (see **Figure 4a**) where the comparison between different materials can be based on a comparison of potentials necessary to drive the reaction to a current density of 1 mA/cm^2 (see **Figure 4b**). All voltammograms used to obtain data presented in **Figure 4b** are summarized in the SI (see **Figure S4**). As the synthesized materials are also morphologically similar, the surface areas of all samples should be comparable in size, particularly, for materials featuring the same A-site cation (see **Fig. S2** in the Supporting Information). This ensures that differences in OER activity can be related to the catalyst's intrinsic activity and are free of the effects of surface blocking with the evolved gas bubbles. The only exception here is the 16 % Ru containing Nd-sample with a significantly larger surface charge of 0.47 mC/cm^2 (cf. SI, **Table S4** and **Figure S5**). However, this material does not conform to the single-phase character and accordingly, its oxygen-evolving activity will not be discussed here.

The potentials at $i = 1 \text{ mA/cm}^2$ are taken as the measure of the intrinsic OER activity of the studied samples. The activity dependence on the chemical composition in the B-site of the pyrochlore structure is shown in **Figure 4b**. The data measured for mixed pyrochlores are complemented by the data reported for pure iridium and ruthenium pyrochlores featuring the same lanthanides in the A-site and nanoparticulate IrO_2 which serves as benchmark catalyst here.[43] It can be seen that all pyrochlores showing the coexistence of Ru and Ir in the B-site need to be driven to the pre-set current density by lower potentials and thus show a superior activity in OER activity than the pyrochlores without cation mixing. Their OER activity also

surpasses that of the benchmark IrO₂ (1.55 V at $i = 1 \text{ mA/cm}^2$). The highest catalytic activity (represented by the potential value of 1.44 V) is encountered for mixed pyrochlores with Ytterbium residing in the A-site. The actual improvement with respect to the benchmark IrO₂ amounts to more than 100 mV in over-potential. It needs to be noted that the same trend is observed also in Tafel plots constructed from chronoamperometric measurements at constant potentials (see **Figure S7** of the Supporting Information).

Figure 4 a) Typical linear sweep voltammograms of pyrochlore based catalyst samples of Ru/Ir mixed composition, measured in acidic media (0.1 M HClO₄, $v = 10 \text{ mV/s}$) and **b)** potential in V vs RHE at a current density of 1 mA/cm^2 (in 0.1 M HClO₄) plotted versus the catalysts’

ruthenium contents as determined by EDX, including the data for the pure lanthanide ruthenates and iridates.

It also needs to be noted that the activity values reported in **Figure 4** are rather high and apparently conflict with the theoretically conceived thermo-neutral potentials reported previously[6]. This apparent discrepancy can be resolved if one reflects the fact that the chronoamperometric data used to extract the activity data are corrected for iR drop affecting the overall energetic balance of the process. One also needs to stress that concept of the thermo-neutral potential also assumes the evolved oxygen to be in standard state (i.e. at pressure of 1 bar). This condition is also unlikely to be met at low current densities when the oxygen solubility cannot be neglected. A more realistic comparison with thermo-neutral potential is then offered by comparing the potential needed to drive the reaction to a higher extent (10 mA/cm²), as is presented in **Figure S6**, Supporting Information. It needs to be stressed that regardless of the current density the activity data show the same qualitative dependence on the chemical composition of the B site and also show significant activity improvement with respect to benchmark catalysts. **The observed catalytic activities represent values averaged by random orientation of the surface. Given the known surface sensitivity of the electrocatalytic processes, one may assume that further optimization of the OER activity might be achieved by a homogenization of the pyrochlore's surface.**

This increased activity of the “mixed” pyrochlores apparently arises from the coexistence of ruthenium and iridium in the B-site and indicates the synergy of the two transition metals. A synergy has previously been reported for IrO₂-RuO₂ core-shell nanoparticles in the oxygen

evolution reaction,[56] but it is unprecedented for the cation mixing of ruthenium and iridium in rutile type oxides, where the addition of Ir to RuO₂ results in a stability improvement with an accompanied activity drop.[32,57] Similarly, for pyrochlore type oxides of (Na_{0.33}Ce_{0.67})₂(Ir_{1-x}Ru_x)O₇ composition the sample with mixed Ru-Ir B-site occupation showed a lower OER activity than the pure Ru-based pyrochlore.[58] Additionally, in contrast to pure pyrochlores,[43] there is no clear effect of the A-site cation size on the OER activity of the mixed pyrochlores (see **Figure 5a-c**) despite the pronounced effect of the A-site cation radius on the XRD-based unit cell parameter. It needs to be noted that the electrocatalytic activity is often related to the d-band center; the position and width ought to be related to the actual catalyst surface and therefore sensitive to the A-site cations size.

Figure 5 OER activity, as potential E_{RHE} at $i = 1 \text{ mA/cm}^2$ measured in 0.1M HClO₄, plotted versus the unit cell parameter resulting from the powder x-ray diffraction patterns of the ytterbium series (a), the gadolinium series (b), and the neodymium series (c). OER activity, as potential E_{RHE} at $i = 1 \text{ mA/cm}^2$ measured in 0.1M HClO₄, plotted versus the different metal-

metal bond lengths of cations residing in the B cationic site as obtained from fitting of the EXAFS data with d) Ru-Ir distance e) Ru-Ru distance f) Ir-Ir distance.

The position of the d-band center of the pyrochlores included in this study is summarized in **Figure 6**. Surprisingly, the DFT provided d-band center values reflect the variations of the pyrochlore structure caused by the A-site cations size only for Ru based pyrochlores featuring no coexistence of Ru and Ir in the B sites. In all other instances, the DFT based d-band center positions seem to be mostly insensitive to the A-site cation size, and their variation results mainly from the coexistence of Ru and Ir in the structure. It needs to be noted that such a prediction contradicts the experimental behavior observed, e.g.; for the Ir based pyrochlores as previously reported.[43] In addition, the center of the d-band seems to increase monotonously towards the Fermi level with the increase of the Ru content.

Figure 6 Position of the d-band center as a function of the Ru content as obtained from DFT calculations of the bulk structures of mixed Ir/Ru pyrochlores. A monotonic up-shift of the d-center is seen independently of the A-site cation.

The monotonous increase of the d-band center is, however, poorly compatible with the activity trends depicted in **Figure 5**, unless one assumes that the mixed pyrochlores with a Ru to Ir ratio of ca. one represent an optimal catalyst residing at the top of the volcano. Unfortunately, such an assumption cannot be proved by a systematic computational investigation of the adsorption energetics of the pyrochlore surfaces due to the prohibitively high computational costs of such an investigation.[43] Also, should the co-existence of Ru and Ir in the structure and connected d-band center variation be responsible for the activation of the catalysts, one should expect similar effects to arise also in rutile type oxides featuring both Ru and Ir. Such behavior is, however, not encountered in experiments.[32,57] Hence, the trends observed in the activity of mixed pyrochlores (see **Fig. 5a**) are difficult to align with the d-band center position despite metal-like conductivity of Ru and Ir based pyrochlores.

The activity of the mixed pyrochlores, on the other hand, seems to correspond to the coexistence of neighboring Ru and Ir in the B-sites as shown by the improvement of the OER activity (see **Fig. 5**) with increasing Ir/Ru mixing (the highest OER activities were measured for the samples with $x_{\text{Ru}}=0.45$ and 0.55 regardless of the A-site cation). The observed trend is also non-linear with respect to the chemical composition suggesting that the oxygen evolution activity of the neighboring Ru-Ir pairs significantly surpasses that of other conceivable surface motifs.

Tafel plots constructed from the steady-state current reading of the chronoamperometric curves at different potentials (see **Figure S7** of the SI) yield Tafel slopes between 44 and 59 mV/decade (**Table 1**). The similarity in the observed Tafel slopes indicates that all prepared materials catalyze the oxygen evolution by the same reaction mechanism. Comparable Tafel slopes, ranging from 46 to 64 mV dec⁻¹, were obtained for the pure lanthanide ruthenium and iridium pyrochlores.[43] Similar Tafel slopes have also been reported frequently for Ru and Ir-based

pyrochlore oxides.[37,38,59] The Tafel slope values are also comparable to those of RuO₂ and IrO₂ (40-60 mV dec⁻¹).[23,26,60–62] Based on microkinetic models, the second electron transfer in the OER mechanism was proposed as rate-determining for these Tafel values.[61,63] It has to be noted, however, that such an assignment is not unambiguous if based solely on the Tafel slope values.[8,62,64]

Table 1 Slopes derived from the Tafel lines of the oxygen evolution on pyrochlore catalysts extracted from steady-state chronoamperometric measurements in 0.1 M HClO₄.

x _{Ru}	Yb [mV dec ⁻¹]	x _{Ru}	Gd [mV dec ⁻¹]	x _{Ru}	Nd [mV dec ⁻¹]
0.70	47 ± 1	0.73	55 ± 2	0.73	50 ± 2
0.58	50 ± 1	0.55	58 ± 3	0.58	51 ± 2
0.45	55 ± 2	0.45	50 ± 1	0.42	55 ± 2
0.15	59 ± 2	0.17	44 ± 1		

The experimentally observed OER activity trends outlined cannot directly be related to the structural parameter based on the diffraction data. They can, however, be related to the local structure as assessed in the EXAFS approach. The observed activity may be correlated with local structure descriptors. Given the above-reported effect of the Ru-Ir pairing, one finds the metal-metal distance of the B-site cations as the most likely structural descriptor (**Figure 5d-f**). It needs to be noted that the choice of the local structure descriptor is based on the assumption that the OER activity is primarily associated with transition metal cations in the B-site. The activity correlates with the iridium-ruthenium distances as shows the linear trend depicted in **Fig. 5d**.

The OER activity increases with decreasing Ru-Ir distance. Hence, it may be expected that the distance of Ru and Ir in the B-site controls the synergy of the catalytic action of mixed pyrochlores. The proximity of ruthenium and iridium was previously discussed and is believed to induce the synergistic effect of the two metals for RuO₂-IrO₂ core-shell nanoparticles.[56] A similar descriptor of the OER activity was also proposed for lanthanide-based perovskites of transition metals.[65] However, one needs to note that the OER activity also correlates rather satisfactorily with the Ru-Ru distance. Such a correlation may be expected though, given the interdependence of Ru-Ru and Ru-Ir distances (see **Figure S3** in the Supporting Information). The OER activity can also be correlated with the Ir-Ir distance. Nevertheless, this correlation is rather unsatisfactory, which disqualifies the Ir-Ir distance as a practically viable descriptor.

The effect of the transition metal spacing on the catalytic activity of the oxides in OER can be rationalized if one accepts an OER mechanism involving the formation of a peroxo μ -bridge between two B-site cations as proposed previously.[9,66,67] Involvement of an O-O bridge intermediate in the mechanism of oxygen evolution has also been proposed for the Mn-based oxygen-evolving complex (OEC) in photosystem II.[68,69] Similar species have been predicted to form on rutile structured oxides in acid media at potentials similar to those applied in this study.[70] The existence of a peroxo μ -bridge was, however, not predicted for oxide-based catalysts featuring a metal-metal distance of ca. 3 Å or shorter. It needs to be noted though that the anticipated formation of bridging peroxo groups needs to be confirmed either computationally or spectroscopically. Direct evidence is, however, still missing due to prohibitive problems encountered in DFT modeling of such f electron-rich systems. Similarly, the available *in-situ* spectroscopic techniques do not offer sufficient surface sensitivity for materials of ca. 100 nm particle size.

Accelerated electrochemical stability tests were performed for the most active pyrochlore samples with a high amount of cation mixing in B-site (ca. 55 % ruthenium). Both the OER current and normalized OER currents are shown in **Figure 7**. There is a significant difference between the behavior of the pyrochlores featuring Nd or Gd and that of the Yb containing pyrochlore. Both the Gd and Nd pyrochlore show a rapid decay of the OER activity with cycling, while the pyrochlore containing Yb displays only a gradual decrease in the OER activity (following a slight activation of ca. 5 % during the first ca. 100 cycles). The mixed pyrochlore featuring Yb retains 90 % of its original activity after 500 cycles, which agrees with the stability of the ytterbium pyrochlores without cation mixing. This material also outperforms the benchmark IrO_2 catalyst (23 % loss).[43] The Gd and Nd containing mixed pyrochlores, however, lose as much as 73 % or 94 % of their initial activity in the same test, respectively.

The activity loss of Gd and Nd containing mixed pyrochlores significantly exceeds that of the pure pyrochlores.[43] The significant difference in the stability of mixed pyrochlores is difficult to relate conclusively to any particular structural feature. Although the best stability is encountered in the case of materials showing the smallest deviation from the ideal pyrochlore structure, the effect of the nature of the lanthanide residing in the A-site also cannot be disregarded.

Figure 7 Electrochemical stability measurements for the mixed Yb, Gd, and Nd pyrochlore samples (Ru content ca. $x_{\text{Ru}}=0.55$) showing the current density (a) and normalized current density at 1.6 V_{RHE} (b) from potential step experiments, including the benchmark catalyst IrO₂.

For a pyrochlore structure to form, a specific ratio of cationic radius A/B has to be matched which has been estimated as 1.36-1.71.[71] For Nd^{III} and Ru^{IV}/Ir^{IV} the A/B ratio is with 1.81 and 1.78, which already exceeds this stability window, while for Gd the ratios of 1.69 and 1.67 are very close to the proposed stability limit. For Ytterbium, however, a very well matching A/B ratio of 1.57 (Ru) and 1.59 (Ir) is obtained which can explain a generally increased stability compared with Gd and Nd. The stability trend Nd < Gd < Yb is also coinciding with the

decreasing basicity[72] of the lanthanide oxides $\text{Nd} > \text{Gd} > \text{Yb}$, indicating a higher dissolution rate of the more basic lanthanides in acidic media and hence lower stability. The activity loss of Gd and Nd containing mixed pyrochlores significantly exceeds that of the pure pyrochlores measured in our previous work,[43] in which degradation of the pyrochlore structure was shown to be the result of preferential dissolution of the A-site cation and, in the cases of materials featuring Ru exclusively in the B-site, Ru dissolution as well. The significant difference in the stability of mixed pyrochlores, however, is difficult to relate conclusively to any particular structural feature.

Conclusions

The coexistence of Ru and Ir in the B-site of the pyrochlore structure substantially affects the catalytic activity of these oxides in the oxygen evolution reaction. The mixed occupation of Ru and Ir in the B-site of the structure apparently leads to a Vegardian-like expansion/contraction of the pyrochlores' lattice. The local structure refined from X-ray absorption spectra shows no clustering of either transition metal in the B-sites. The EXAFS based refined metal-metal distances reveal, however, significant deviations from an ideal pyrochlore structure in which one finds equal distances between all cations. All spray-freeze freeze-drying prepared mixed pyrochlores are highly active in OER and outperform the pure ruthenium and iridium pyrochlores as well as the iridium oxide benchmark catalyst. The highest oxygen evolution activity was detected for samples with a high mixing of transition metal cations in B-site.

To reach the reference current density of $i = 1 \text{ mA/cm}^2$, these materials need a ca. 100 mV lower over-potential than the benchmark IrO_2 catalyst. The OER activity of the mixed cations apparently does not scale with the diffraction-based lattice parameter which contradicts the

generally accepted d-band center concept. The OER activity, on the other hand, increases with decreasing Ru-Ir distance. This suggests that the OER may involve a formation of a peroxo μ -bridge intermediate in a manner similar to Photosystem II. The viability of such a mechanism, however, needs to be backed with theoretical modeling. The trends observed in the OER activity stress the importance of a synergetic operation of neighboring Ru and Ir as well as a role of local structure in the oxygen evolution process. The increased catalytic activity of mixed pyrochlores is accompanied by excellent stability if the A-site is occupied by Yb. These materials retain 90 % of its original activity after 500 cycles. The stability of the Gd and Nd containing mixed pyrochlores is, however, less satisfactory. Nevertheless, the Yb stabilized mixed pyrochlores successfully address both major hindrances of the OER catalysts for acid media applications –the high price of Ir and the unsatisfactory stability of Ru-based catalysts - at the same time.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information

Details of the Rietveld refinement, plot of nominal vs. actual composition, SEM micrographs and particle size analysis, details of the EXAFS refinement, and plot of individual metal-metal distances as a function of Ru-Ru distance, voltammograms, surface charges, Tafel plots from chronoamperometry are included in the Supporting Information (PDF).

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The manuscript was written through contributions of all authors. All authors have given approval to the final version of the manuscript.

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